

N, P, and K uptake of rice on coastal saline soils

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We studied N, P, and K uptake in CSR4 rice on coastal saline soil. Three

levels of N (0, 50, 100 kg/ha), P (0, 25, 50 kg/ha), and K (0, 25, 50 kg/ha) were tried in 3³ factorial design. Initial ECe was 3.0-12.0 dS/m, pH 7.1, available N 295 kg, P 23.5 kg, and K 490 kg/ha.

P and K response and NPK interaction did not significantly affect grain yield. N effect on yield was highly significant at all levels in all the seasons, yielding 3.0, 3.9, and 4.3 t/ha in wet season and 2.8, 3.5, and 3.8 t/ha in dry season.

Uptake of N increased with increased application levels in both seasons; the increase was higher in wet season than in dry (see figure).

Although the yield effects of P and K were insignificant, the uptake of those nutrients was positive and increasing, especially with high levels of N.

Lower assimilation of these nutrients, especially N, in dry season than in the wet season might be due to soil salinity. □

Uptake of N, P, and K at different N levels. CSSRI, India.

Effect of N and *Azospirillum* on rice N uptake

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We conducted a pot experiment in Entisols of Indo-Gangetic alluvium (pH 7.2, 0.043% total soil N, 5.0 ppm Olsen P, 103 ppm 1 N NH₄ OAc K) with 4 N levels (0, 15, 30, and 45 ppm) and *Azospirillum* (*A. brasilense*) inoculation on Saket 4. Earthen pots

lined with polyethylene sheets were filled with 10 kg soil and basal dressing of 13.0 ppm P and 25.0 ppm K through single superphosphate and muriate of potash. Ammonium sulfate was the N source.

Roots of 22-d-old seedlings were dipped in carrier-based inoculant slurry and seedlings transplanted at 5/pot. Yield was recorded, grain analyzed for N content, and uptakes calculated.

N increased grain yield, grain N content, and N uptake. The highest values were associated with 45 ppm N (see table). Each N increment

Effect of applied N and *Azospirillum* on rice N uptake.

Treatment	Grain yield (g/pot)	Grain N (%)	N uptake (mg/pot)
Control (no N)	16.2	1.60	259.2
15 ppm N	21.5	1.66	356.9
30 ppm N	26.2	1.78	466.3
45 ppm N	30.0	1.87	561.0
<i>A. brasilense</i>	18.2	1.64	298.4
LSD (5%)	2.2	0.01	4.4

increased the parameters. N fixation and production of growth-promoting substances by *Azospirillum* might have contributed to improved root mass, thereby increasing grain yields and N uptake. □